

The Influence of Social Media Advertising Values on Consumers Purchasing Intention in Somalia

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ABSTRACT

Background of the problem: Due to the absence of internet facilities and strangeness on the part of regional customers, particularly the countryside and some states residences are not aware of social media advertising existence, social media advertising is still at the beginning of advancement Somalia. **Main objective:** This study's main objective is to understand the impact of social media advertising on the purchase intention of consumers in Mogadishu-Somalia by employing Ducoffe's advertising value model. **Research methods:** a quantitative study was used, and the participants totalled 182. The data was collected using a convenience sampling technique. A structured questionnaire was utilized to gather the data through the social media platform, especially Facebook and WhatsApp and analysed employing exploratory factor analysis and multi regression analysis. **Findings:** Results signify that there is a significant relationship between informativeness, entertainment, credibility, the overall perceived value of social media advertising and the purchase intention of consumers who are living in Mogadishu-Somalia. **Contribution:** Social media marketers in Mogadishu-Somalia should develop an innovative, cutting-edge, information-rich, full entertainment of social media advertising, maintain the trustworthiness of their ad's campaigns, and enhance the perceived value of social media ads to lure and urge the purchase intention of the consumers. **Conclusion:** All the independent factors (informativeness, entertainment, credibility, and perceived value of social media advertising) have a positive impact on consumers' purchase intention. Therefore, it is recommended for marketing professionals to carefully plan and design their advertising campaigns to lure their target audiences' attention.

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Introduction

The fast evolution of the internet and the information and communication of modern technologies have heightened a considerable increase of social media sites in the two decades. Besides, social media sites' consistent development showed to be the most massive movements throughout the internet, where around 90% of internet users are actively using social networking sites (We Are Social & Hootsuite, 2021). Social media nowadays is not only a communication tool, However, it is still an essential aspect of a company's marketing strategies. (Moslehpour et al., 2020). These platforms enhance customer value by offering valuable content on a good or service and promoting it (Hansopaheluwakan et al., 2020). Ghafourzay & Parilti (2020), suggested that social networking sites have made it easier for individuals to interact with one another and make friends virtually. Moreover, social media became the most important platform that facilitates communication between people, especially Somalia youth, who frequently use them.

Somalia is a country located in east Africa, and it is bordered by Kenya to the south west, Ethiopia to the west, the golf Aden to the north, Djibouti to the northwest, and the Indian ocean to the east. According to UNFPA Somalia (2019), most Somalis are in their adolescent and youth years, accounting for 75% of the total population, indicating that these are digital-oriented people who are heavily connected to the internet and social media since technology became an integral part of our daily life (Ahmed & Kising'u, 2019). Even though the marketing efforts of businesses in Somalia heavily rely on traditional media such as TV, radios, and magazines, corporations need to be where their target audience is to capture and attract their intent. Social media can help companies in Somalia, on the one hand, to evaluate interconnectivity between business and customers by collecting feedback from customers on future company offers

(Sharawneh, 2020). In contrast to conventional ads, Aji et al. (2020) argued that social media ads concurrently provides information, promotes deals, and responds to consumer requests, also, it is a cost-effective medium of marketing and advertising goods and services. Besides that, Kaplan & Haenlein (2010) stated that social networks offer companies a way to participate in the conversation timely and promptly contact their customers. Therefore, social media sites have been used as an advertising tool to strengthen the connection between brands and their clients, consequently establishing more reliable relationships between both sides (Moslehpour et al., 2020).

Advertisers and businesses have begun to gain these media's advantages for promoting products and investing more energies and budgets in social media advertising (Chi, 2011). However, most Somalia businesses have social media accounts and make posts about their products and services. Still, they have not taken the benefits of social media advertising since they do not use any advertising campaigns in social media such as Facebook ads, Google AdWords, YouTube ads, etc. Nevertheless, the growth of attractiveness in social media advertising globally has brought about the inquiry of whether it is regarded as valuable (Hamouda, 2018). The value of advertising describes a subjective assessment of the commercial's usability to customers in total (Ducoffe, 1995). This means the success of the promoted product or service depends on the satisfaction of intended customers. A bulk of consumers understand the informative and entertaining functions of advertising. The commercial must provide detailed information about the advertised product and conveys enjoyment to encourage a reliable interaction between the advertisers and customers. Thus, the two most durable measurements of consumers' beliefs about advertising are informativeness and entertainment (Ducoffe, 1995). Furthermore, as Dao et al. (2014), argued

that the trustworthy of advertisement also perceived as an essential indicator for the social media advertising value in consumers' mind. Therefore, informativeness, entertainment, and credibility are deemed to be as customers' social media advertising belief.

Hence, there is tremendous interest from academic scholars and practitioners related to social media advertising values (Saxena & Khanna, 2013). However, to get a comprehensive understanding of social media advertising for utilizing a successful marketing communication system, many researchers have currently embraced several studies about it (Dao et al., 2014). Regardless of expanding literature on social media advertising, inevitable shortages can be revealed, especially in Somalia. First, social media advertising studies in Somalia are still at the beginning stage with several undetermined findings and divergent outcomes. Secondly, Online advertisement is constantly evolving, indicating that the body of knowledge around social media advertising will continue to evolve as the usage of social media platforms grows (Zhang & Mao, 2016). Furthermore, most of these existing studies are carried out in developed and developing economic countries where the internet service is relatively stable and customers are more exposed to social media ads in areas (Dao et al., 2014), unlike Somalia.

Moreover, due to the absence of internet facilities and strangeness on the part of regional customers particularly countryside and some states residences are not aware with the existence of social media advertising. According to the researchers' best knowledge, there is limited and insufficient literature about the influence of social media advertising values on purchase intention among consumers in Somalia. Therefore, regarding the above discussions, further research is required to be conducted to

fill the existing gap. by utilizing the advertising value model developed by Ducoffe (1996) as a theoretical framework, this study intends to deal with these gaps as well as attempt to strengthen the existing understanding of the effect of social media advertising on customers' purchase intention in Somalia.

The study's general objective is to recognize the impact of the elements of social media advertising values on the purchase intentions of the consumers that will generate a positive consumer perspective. More specifically, the study investigates the following objectives: First, to identify the impact of the informativeness of social media advertising on the consumer's purchase intention in Somalia. Second, to examine the effect of the entertainment of social media advertising on the consumer's purchase intention in Somalia. Third, to investigate the impact of the credibility of social media advertising on the consumer's purchase intention in Somalia. And lastly, to examine the influence of the overall perceived value of social media advertising on the consumer's purchase intention in Somalia.

Hence, the article is organized accordingly—first, a theoretical consideration of the key concepts used to develop the research model and hypotheses. Literature has been discussed about social media advertising, the antecedents of social media advertising, including informativeness, entertainment, credibility, and the overall values of social media advertising. The next step will describe the methodology by providing the criteria for Facebook's selection as social media advertising, sampling process description, measurements, data collection and analysis for the study model are also discussed. The results of the study and the critical research findings will be addressed. Afterwards, the article presents theoretical and practical implications, limitations, and future directions for research.

Literature Review

Theoretical Foundation

As indicated by [Fishbein \(1963\)](#), Expectancy Value theory describes the response about an object depends on the person's belief. The theory suggests that belief is a subjective understanding of a person about something (e.g., social media advertising) connected to the features of that thing (e.g., entertainment). A belief is generated when the relationship between an object and a particular attribute a person has to agree with. When the belief goes up, the anticipated value of an object that the person perceives and beliefs can be developed represents the expectancy elements of Expectancy Value theory ([Smith & Swinyard, 1982](#)).

The idea of advertising value was suggested in 1995 by Ducoffe; it is described as customers' view of the usability or the relative importance of the ad. Ducoffe proposed an advertisement value model focused on three components of advertising value: informativeness, entertainment, and irritation, which indicated a positive association between advertising value and attitude toward advertising. A further factor was developed, which has a favourable bond with advertising value, which is credibility ([Brackett & Carr, 2001](#)). Likewise, according to [Murillo et al. \(2016\)](#), the advertising value model is the most extensively utilized concept to clarify client understandings and perspectives toward advertising. [Murillo et al. \(2016\)](#) also stated that the irritation factor has currently been identified as a weak predictor of advertisement value. Other studies (e.g., [Dao et al., 2014](#); [Hamouda, 2018](#)) have included one more significant factor that affects the consumers' buying intention, which is the credibility of social media advertising value. However, in this study, it is also added another factor to understand its impact on consumers purchase intention, and this factor is the overall perceived value of social media advertising. Therefore, informativeness, entertainment, credibility, and overall perceived

value of social media advertising appear to choose the best significant predictors of consumers' purchase intention in Somalia.

Social Media Advertising

The fast development of social media platforms has wholly transformed how many consumers communicate with one another and companies ([Ajina, 2019](#)). Thus, this has transformed the method that companies bring in and keep potential customers ([Leung et al., 2015](#)). As [Kaplan & Haenlein \(2010\)](#), defined social media is "a group of internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0 and that allow the creation and exchange of User Generated Content". In simple terms, social media are platforms that allow individuals to engage by forming personal information profile, welcoming colleagues and partners to get gain access to those profiles and exchange messages between them. However, [Kaplan & Haenlein \(2010\)](#) have also suggested six classifications of social media based on a set of theories in the field of media research (social presence, media richness) and social process (self-presentation, self-disclosure). The categories are social networking sites (e.g., Facebook and Instagram), collaborate projects (e.g., Wikipedia), content communities (e.g., SlideShare and YouTube), Blogs, virtual social world (e.g., second life), and virtual game worlds (e.g., the world of warcraft).

Social media usage has been experiencing an increase in both individuals and companies ([Eid et al., 2019](#)). According to [Hootsuite & WeAreSocial \(2020\)](#), global internet users have surpassed 4.5 billion, and of those, 3.8 billion users are now active in social media. Moreover, internet users have spent an average of six hours and forty-three minutes every day online globally. Among those, they spent two hours and twenty-four minutes on social media per day across all devices, and this is accounting for -

more than one-third of our total internet time. In Somalia, internet users have surpassed 1.63 million, and among those, 1.6 are actively using social media ([We Are Social & Hootsuite, 2020](#)). Hence, Firms could market their products, develop awareness, construct consideration, and obtain customer buy-in at nearly one-tenth the expense of traditional advertising and marketing. In fact, social media makes it possible for the business to enhance their marketing and advertising techniques in numerous ways ([Ebrahim, 2020](#)). For example, social media is a method for collecting information from the customers which might be evaluated and also utilized afterwards to forecast the volume of future discussions on social media as well as even to prepare for and anticipate future issues around the complete task of the business ([Singh & Duhan, 2016](#)).

However, [Mir \(2012\)](#) argued that social media has helped businesses to develop and build reliable connections with their clients, which leads to improving their corporate and brand image. It also changed the traditional ways of marketing communication strategies that firms use to influence their target audience ([Mangold & Faulds, 2009](#)), because social media has both types of advertising, explicit advertising and implicit advertising ([Taylor et al., 2011](#)). Social media advertising confirms that it is more intriguing because it allows users to search for recommendations and shared experiences with other consumers with little effort. Over the last decade, firms have spent advertising on social media spaces, such as Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, and Facebook, to advertise their products or services ([Patino et al., 2012](#)). According to [Enberg \(2019\)](#), businesses have spent \$333.25 billion globally advertising for their products or services through social media, and it is expected to reach \$517.51 billion in 2023. This illustrates that social media has an incredible source of advertising which enable firms to get more customers.

Informativeness of SMA and Purchase Intention

The informativeness of advertising in social media can be termed as the capability of advertising to notify customers of different product or service information, which enable the clients to make alternatives with the highest value ([Ducoffe, 1996](#)). Also, Informativeness is related to ads' ability to educate customers about the features and benefits of the products ([Arora & Agarwal, 2019](#)). Informativeness is viewed as the degree to which the business can provide adequate information about the products or services to the customers to make better buying decisions. Individuals are moving away from conventional advertising outlets and instead relying on social media sites to keep up with the latest updates about the brands and their products. Since it's more convenient and can be accessed at any time, customers search for information online ([Sari et al., 2020](#)). In Somalia, the combination of limited knowledge of brands and the availability of the product has increased the need for the information of the product by the consumers, since one of the most important inspirations for utilizing social networks is searching for and information exchanging ([Muntinga et al., 2011](#)). Therefore, customers intentionally look for social media advertising as it represents an appropriate mechanism for such objective by its layout that offers a display of individual contacts and further product information, frequently supported by video clips and photos. ([Dao et al., 2014](#)).

According to [Saxena & Khanna \(2013\)](#), if the ad provides more information about the product to the consumer, like, details about the products' advantages, and features, the more result it has on this advertisement value. The informativeness level in social media sites ads can encourage consumers to have much better-purchasing behaviour and might appropriately boost their purpose to purchase. The study of [Sari et al. \(2020\)](#) found that the informativeness of social media advertising has a positive and significant -

influence on Muslim millennial parents' purchase intention. Similarly, [Arora & Agarwal \(2020\)](#) had empirically investigated the effectiveness of social media advertising and found that informativeness significantly affects the purchase intention of Indian millennial consumers. Additionally, research done by Taylor et al. (2011) found that there is a favourable connection between the informativeness of the ads in social media and client's attitudes.

Furthermore, [Lee et al. \(2006\)](#) empirically confirmed the favourable role of advertising informativeness on clients' response toward social media advertising, and subsequently, on their intention to purchase the products provided in the social networks advertising. Therefore, in line with Expectancy Value theory and the above literature evidence, consumers in Somalia are anticipated to consider social media advertising as informative, leading to a positive purchase intention. So, it is hypothesized the following hypothesis:

H1: Social media advertising informativeness will affect consumer's purchase intention of the promoted product.

Entertainment of SMA And Purchase Intention

Generally, advertising is most likely to please customer hedonic requirements by supplying enjoyment, emotional release, diversion, and satisfaction. Advertising entertainment is the congeniality of an ad, in addition to the enjoyment and the pleasure of the target audience stem from the advertising ([Hamouda, 2018](#)). An ad's ability to entertain is recognized as one of the significant aspects that can influence the commercial's efficiency in developing a psychological connection among customers and brand message ([Wang & Sun, 2010](#)).

By fueling this, the primary factors for utilizing social media by individuals are getting relaxation, pleasure, and passing the time, as reported by ([Muntinga et al., 2011](#)). Social media are commonly recognized as modern entertainment

outlets where hedonic expectations can be fulfilled. Because of their attitude and desire levels, consumers are more attracted to social media advertising, and they will engage in more hedonic social media experiences ([Sarraf & Teshnizi, 2020](#)). Moreover, customers anticipate that social media advertising material gives them enjoyment values that rely on the ads' exceptional designs, such as message appeals, interactivity, and direct digital experience, prominent on social networks sites ([Zhang & Mao, 2016](#)). However, with the market cluttered with advertising messages trying to capture people's focus, an advertisement requires to be fascinating as well as delightful in an innovative way to draw in target markets' attention.

Furthermore, the advertising's entertainment values will undoubtedly make customers experience the feeling action in the ad processing. Evidence has revealed that entertainment values influence or sharply influence customers' mindset towards internet advertisements ([Zhang & Mao, 2016](#)) and ads on social media sites ([Taylor et al., 2011](#)). The entertainment materials in advertising excite passion ([Wang & Sun, 2010](#)). Hence, the advertisements with more incredible visual and enjoyment complexity tend to create a much more favourable mindset in people and might additionally positively influence their purchasing behaviour toward the promoted product or brand ([Ducoffe, 1995](#)). Hence, the entertainment of social media advertising has a positive influence on the ads' attitude, which brings a favourable decision to purchase the advertised product ([Shareef et al., 2017](#)). A study by [Cahyani & Artanti \(2020\)](#) found that social media advertising's entertainment has a significant impact on customer purchase intention. Apart from that, [Sarraf & Teshnizi \(2020\)](#) examined the impact of social media advertising properties on buying intention and concluded that entertainment positively influences consumers' buying intention. In line with expectancy-value theory, customers will successively consider the ability of social media ads to entertain intuitively, if the ads in social media create an emotional connection with clients, and simplifies their delight, gratification, and entertainment clients will appreciate and check anticipated benefits from advertising which brings to positive purchase

intention. Therefore, based on the above, this study articulates the following hypothesis:

H2: Social media advertising entertainment will affect consumer's purchase intention of the promoted product.

Credibility of SMA and Purchase Intention

MacKenzie & Lutz (1989) defined advertising credibility is the sincerity, plausibility, and reliability of the offered content of promotion as recognized by customers. Zha et al. (2015) stated that credibility plays a considerable function in identifying promotion performance and its value. The increase in trust for online media results from its ability to honest and open information by offering testimonials and scores from other consumers (O'Connor et al., 2016). According to Yang et al. (2013), clients may stay clear of or stop working to react to promotions if they question their authenticity. Advertising credibility can influence customers' feelings and their purchasing intention (Jin & Villegas, 2007). However, developing reliable content of advertising is very important for the ads to be effective. Chu & Kim (2011) stated that, in social media advertising, the advertising materials are regarded as trustworthy and reliable because discussions on current social links are showed and cooperated with the web content. Furthermore, Arora and Agarwal (2020) has asserted that putting a trust in social media platforms is necessary before trusting any information being displayed it. On top of that, the content credibility of social network is significant as it shows whether or not the contents on that social network can be considered as believable (Lai and Liu, 2019). This is in line with Gaber, Wright and Kooli (2019), who agreed that the marketers must be cautious about the trustworthiness of the contents they are sharing on social media.

Mangold & Faulds (2009) recommend that social networks ads are considered a legitimate source of product information and significantly considered by clients. Most customers perceive

social media advertising as a source of information, saving time and energy for seeking information about the intended products to buy. Therefore, social media advertising's perceived benefits are reliable information, time-saving, and energy (Dao et al., 2014). Wang & Sun (2010) argued that when customers believe that the social media ads are trustworthy and dependable, they are more optimistic about online advertisements, which enhances their purchase intention about the promoted product or service.

Furthermore, Sari et al. (2020) suggested that social media advertising credibility significantly influences the consumer's purchase intention. Consistent with expectancy-value theory, the customers will instinctively evaluate the trustworthiness and credibility of social media advertising via various other participants' comments of the current social media networks community members within the advertising (Okazaki, 2004). Customers in Somalia can thus clarify the credibility and the reliability of ads in social media and generate credibility on the ads, which leads to positive purchase intention. Therefore, the study suggested that:

H3: Social media advertising credibility will affect consumer's purchase intention of the promoted product.

Overall Perceived Value of SMA And Purchase Intention

Purchase intentions can be described as a customer's intention to try to acquire a product. It is a crucial index for the assessment of customer's actions. Purchase intention is the level or possibility the customer would be willing to acquire a service or product. Likewise, it can measure the likelihood of a consumer to acquire a product, and the greater the purchase intent, the higher a consumer's desire to purchase a product (Harshini C, 2015). Purchase intention is conceived as customers' plan to purchase from a company (Schlosser et al., 2006). Additionally, the consumer's decision-making process can be

influenced by some implementations of marketing communication such as advertising and promotion contents (Raji, Rashid and Ishak, 2019). Moreover, Aziza and Astuti (2019) claimed that consumers perceived the social media advertising have the ability to convey information about alternatives products or services, in which it could provide a possible satisfaction to the consumers.

It appears that advertising values serve as an emotional function of the customers for the utility of ads. Hence, based on the elements in the discussions mentioned above, social media advertising is potentially valuable, and customers are most likely to react favorably to the promoted product. At some point, the perceived value of social media advertising might promote or enhance the advertiser's goods' purchase intention (Dao et al., 2014). The Expectancy Value Theory framework additionally backs up

the claim, as mentioned above, that consumers' general assessment feedback about the product

can ultimately impact their behavioral reaction about that product. However, the value of advertising performs a significant function in developing a favorable attitude of consumers toward the ads in a social media environment (Ducoffe, 1996). The result of a favorable perspective to the promotion thus brings about an optimistic attitude towards the promoted brand (Goldsmith et al., 2000). It ultimately creates customers' purchase intention towards the brand's products (Choi & Rifon, 2002). Chen and Lin (2019) have found that social media marketing activities has a significant impact on perceived value, in which it can have an effect on participation intention, satisfaction, continuance intention, as well as buying intention. Besides that, the perceptions of consumers towards the advertising value may also create the tendency for consumers for impulse buying (Dodoo and Wu, 2019). Based on that, the following hypothesis will be suggested by the study

H4: Perceived overall value of social media advertising has a positive influence on the promoted product's purchase intention.

The Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Research Methodology

Design, sample, and data collection

The research approach to be used in this study is quantitative research with a descriptive research design to meet the study's objectives. The study is based on the positivism research philosophy since the researchers aim to concentrate on the influence of social media advertising values toward the consumers' purchasing intention. The area to be conducted the study is in Somalia by using a

convenience sampling approach; this method accelerated collecting the data and empowered the researchers to communicate with the participants who are obtainable and keen to participate in the study. Furthermore, due to the widespread of the deadly virus (COVID-19), it is challenging to collect the respondents' data physically since the individuals fear physical contact. Therefore, convenience sampling is the best choice for collecting the data by distributing the questionnaire (English version) through social media, especially Facebook and WhatsApp.

Facebook was chosen as the social media advertising platform; numerous factors are favouring this decision. First, with more than 2.7 billion people in 2021, Facebook is a prevalent platform worldwide. Then, it is easy for such users and visitors to find adequate respondents (Hamouda, 2018). Facebook is also the largest social media platform, which most Somali's use compared to others. Similarly, most companies in Somalia do marketing campaigns and promotion through Facebook. So, under this study, it is argued that Facebook users in Somalia are well suited to be the study's target audience.

However, the total number of social media users in Somalia is 1.6 million, and the people that Facebook reports can be reached with adverts on Facebook have reached 1.5 million users, which counted for 93% of total users (Hootsuite & WeAreSocial, 2020). Slovin's sampling formula was used to calculate the study's sample size; a 204 sample size was used for data collection; after being reshuffling and removing the missing data, 182 respondents were used as the final answers to the questionnaire.

Measure. All the questionnaire measurements were adapted from prior studies with minor adjustments to suit the present situation. The five items in the constructs of informativeness were employed from (Logan et al., 2012). The four items in the entertainment constructs, the three items in the credibility constructs, and the three items in the perceived value of social media advertising constructs have been adapted (Dao et al., 2014). And lastly, the four items selected to measure the purchase intention of the promoted products through social media have been taken (Duffett, 2015).

Data Analysis

The study analyses the data. Descriptive frequencies and descriptive statistics are considered and reported to determine the characteristics of the sample taken. And this followed by a reliability analysis to ensure the internal consistency for each of the questionnaire's constructs. Additionally, the study performs factor analysis with (KMO and Bartlett's test, Factor loading, and Eigenvalues), and finally, multi-regression analysis for hypotheses testing. All the results are run by using SPSS software v.23.

Results

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1: Characteristics of the sample

Sample (n=182)

Items	Frequency	Per cent %
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Gender		
Male	132	72.5
Female	50	27.5
Marital Status		
Single	138	76
Married	44	24
Age		
18 – 24	96	52.7
25 – 34	80	44
35 – 44	6	3.3
Educational Level		
High school	6	3.3
Diploma	5	2.7
University Degree	100	55
Post-graduate	71	39
Occupation		
Employed	85	46.7
Not employed	18	9.9
Self-employed	19	10.4
Student	60	33
Facebook membership		
Less than six months	2	1.1
Six months to 1 year	2	1.1
One year – two years	5	2.7
Above two years	173	95.1
Facebook usage frequency		
Daily	148	81.3
Weekly	22	12.1

Less often	12	6.6
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The overall time spent on Facebook

> 30 minutes	47	25.8
Between 30 minutes and 1 hour	40	22
1 hour to 2 hours	48	26.4
Above two hours	47	25.8

The data was collected from Somali Facebook users through an online survey, and as shown in Table 1, a sample of 182 was obtained. The sample included a slight majority of males, around 72.5%, as compared to the females with 27.5%, and most of the participants' marital status was single with 76%. The respondents' age who mostly participated in this study is between 18 – 24 and 25 – 34 years old, with 52.7% and 44%, respectively. Moreover, in much of the sample, 55% had a bachelor's level of education.

In comparison, high school and diploma had 6% collectively, and most of the sample was employed with 46.7% as compared to students of 33%. Most participants had more than two years of experience on Facebook and usually used it daily, as the results of Facebook membership and frequency of use has shown, 95.1% and 81.3%, respectively. And lastly, around 50% reported they spent an hour on Facebook per day as compared to those who use more than 2 hours daily, around one-fifths.

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis Summary

Variable	No	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Informativeness	182				
INF ₁		1	5	4.05	1.150
INF ₂		1	5	3.83	.980
INF ₃		1	5	3.84	.932
INF ₄		1	5	3.61	1.086
INF ₅		1	5	3.51	1.106
Entertainment	182				
ENT ₁		1	5	3.25	.997
ENT ₂		1	5	3.42	1.009
ENT ₃		1	5	3.42	1.036
ENT ₄		1	5	3.77	1.107
Credibility	182				

CRE ₁	1	5	3.32	.997
CRE ₂	1	5	3.12	1.070
CRE ₃	1	5	3.34	1.059
Overall Advertising Value	182			
OAV ₁	1	5	3.92	.966
OAV ₂	1	5	3.72	.925
OAV ₃	1	5	3.97	1.005
Purchase Intention	182			
PI ₁	1	5	3.53	1.044
PI ₂	1	5	3.48	.973
PI ₃	1	5	3.60	.921
PI ₄	1	5	3.71	.914

As presented in Table 2, Mean and standard deviation were computed for all scale items used in the current study. All items in the informativeness of social media advertising were observed to have a mean value of more than 3.5 with standard deviation values less than 1.150. This means that the current study respondents positively valued the informativeness of social media advertising. Likewise, the lowest mean for entertainment items was ENT₁ (3.25), with a standard deviation value of 0.997. Accordingly, it could be said that the respondents of the current study sample have average entertainment toward social media ads. Credibility items were also normally

valued by most respondents with mean values not less than 3.12, and standard deviation values not higher than 1.070. Also, most of the respondents' overall perceived value of social media advertising is viewed as necessary since all the items have a mean value of over 3.72 with a standard deviation of under 1.005. Lastly, the consumer's purchase intention items have an average value above 3.48 with a standard deviation under 1.044. therefore, participants of this study usually seem interested in buying such products in social media advertising.

Reliability Analysis

Table 3: Reliability Analysis

			Sample: 182
Variables	Number of Items	Cronbach α	
Overall constructs	19	0.850	
Informativeness	5	.671	
Entertainment	4	.630	
Credibility	3	.746	

The perceived value of SMA	3	.814
Purchase intention	4	.805

As table 3 shows, reliability analysis was conducted on overall variables and each of the constructs to check its internal consistency. The result showed that the overall constructs have 0.850 internal consistency with 19 items, and each construct's alpha is above 0.60. Therefore,

according to Pallant (2007), the minimum Cronbach alpha that is acceptable to proceed for further analysis must be 0.6. As such, the internal consistency of the variables is above 0.6 and deemed for further analysis.

Exploratory Factor Analysis

Table 4: KMO & Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser Meyer Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.822
	Approx. Chi-Square	1098.640
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	153
	Sig.	.000

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test Sphericity were observed, as shown in Table 4, to study the sample's adequacy and the correlations between the variables. In this study, KMO was 0.822 and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

was significant at $p < 0.001$, showing that the current data was appropriate for factor analysis. There are sufficient correlations among the variables of the study.

Table 5: Factor Analysis

Items	Components				
	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5
	Informativeness of SMA	Entertainment of SMA	Credibility of SMA	Overall Perceived Values	Purchase intention
INFO2	.821				
INFO4	.668				
INFO3	.613				
INFO1	.590				

ENT3		.789			
ENT2		.659			
ENT4		.571			
CRE2			.805		
CRE1			.769		
CRE3			.640		
OPV 1				.819	
OPV 2				.769	
OPV 3				.760	
PI3					.844
PI4					.797
PI2					.697
PI1					.669
Initial Eigenvalue	5.306	1.777	1.667	1.278	1.200
% of Variance	29.478	9.873	9.260	7.100	6.668
Cumulative %	29.478	39.352	48.612	55.711	62.380

As a result of the table above shown, five factors had eigenvalues more than one. In short, 19 item structures were found to explain 62.380 per cent of the data variance, as shown in **Table 5**. The first factor accounted for 29.478 per cent of the total variance with an eigenvalue of 5.306. Factor loading for items in this criterion was ranged from 0.444-0.821; therefore, the first factor reflects the informativeness of social media advertising. Next, the second factor accounted for 9.873 per cent of the total variance with an eigenvalue of 1.777; the factor loading for items in this criterion ranged from 0.571-0.789; however, one item in this criterion was also

removed because it loaded to another factor. Hence, the second factor reflects the entertainment of social media advertising.

The third factor accounted for 9.260% of the total variance with an eigenvalue of 1.667; the factor loading for items in this criterion ranged from 0.640-0.805; hence, the third factor reflects social media's credibility advertising. Moreover, the fourth factor was the overall perceived value of social media advertising, and it accounted for 7.100% of the total variance with an eigenvalue of 1.278. The items in this factor have factor loading ranged from 0.760-0.819. Finally, the last

factor in this study is consumers' purchase intention, and it accounted for 6.668% of the total variance with an eigenvalue of 1.200. The

factor loading for items in this criterion ranged from 0.669-0.844. Based on the results of exploratory factor analysis, this study is suitable to make further analysis.

Multi Regression Analysis

Table 6: Multi regression analysis

Hypothesis	Regression weights	B	t	p-value	Hypothesis accepted or rejected
H1	INFO—PI	.185	2.316	0.022	Accepted
H2	ENT—PI	.225	2.048	0.044	Accepted
H3	CRE—PI	.192	2.803	0.006	Accepted
H4	OPV—PI	.231	3.201	0.002	Accepted
R ²	0.257				
F (4,177)	15.316				

Multi regression analysis was conducted to assess the strength of the relationship between four independent variables: informativeness, entertainment, credibility, and overall perceived social media advertising and one dependent variable, which is the consumers' purchase intention in Somalia. The dependent variable (Purchase intention) was regressed on predicting variables of informativeness, entertainment, credibility, and overall perceived values of social media advertising. The independent variables have significantly predicted the consumers' purchase intention, $F(4,177) = 15.316$, $p < 0.05$, which indicates that the four factors under the study have a significant influence on the customers' purchase intention. This means that whenever the social media marketers enhance the advertisement's values, such as the quality of information the ads convey, its enjoyments, the trustworthiness of ads, and the perceived value of social media advertising, the consumers' purchase intention increase. Furthermore, the $R^2 = 0.257$ depicts that the model explains 25.7% of

the purchase intention variance. The above table shows a summary of the findings.

Discussion

The study was performed to uncover the primary aspects of social media advertising that might influence consumers' buying intention. Undoubtedly, companies in this modern world invest a great deal of money and dedication in advertising their products by utilizing social media platforms. As necessary, there is continuously worry concerning such campaigns' usefulness and how these efforts can draw in more clients. Furthermore, [Dwivedi et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Shareef et al. \(2017\)](#) argued that social media promotions need to be created and arranged to consider all the essential aspects that emphasize customer attention. Therefore, a closely reviewed of the main literary works related to marketing and advertisements and social media led this research to recognize four aspects (informativeness, home entertainment, reliability, and overall perceived value of social

media advertising) as vital predictors of the purchase intention of the consumers.

Based on the study's findings, the informativeness of social media advertising has a significant favorable impact on the consumers' purchase intention as the path coefficient value is ($B=0.18$ and $p<0.005$). This indicates that social media advertising should deliver fully informed about the product's features and benefits since the customers are looking for informative content about the product before making the purchasing decision. Therefore, if the ads provide the basic features and benefits of the promoted product, it positive influence the consumers' purchase intention, which in turn brings that consumers would react positively and buy the product from the sponsored brand. However, many studies have concluded that social media advertising's informativeness has a positive impact on purchase intention (Ducoffe, 1995; Dao et al., 2014; Shareef et al., 2017; Alalwan, 2018; Arora & Agarwal, 2020).

Entertainment of social media advertising has positive and significant impacts on the consumers' purchase intention as the outcomes of the study have shown that the path coefficient value was ($B=0.225$) and the p-value is less than 0.005. This happened because social media is a place of entertainment and enjoyment, so customers seek engaging and entertaining content that may influence their purchase intention. Therefore, companies are called to develop and design their advertisements more ingeniously and innovatively. Furthermore, the basic landscape of social media applications is considered by a greater level of uniqueness, which subsequently offers consumers a new and different experience over these systems, providing a lot more joy and entertainment. Additionally, several studies have also supported that the entertainment social media advertising has a favourable effect on consumers' purchase intention (Dao et al., 2014; Lee & Hong, 2016; Shareef et al., 2017; Alalwan, 2018).

This study also supports the third hypothesis as the path coefficient value and P-value is ($B=0.192$ and $p<0.005$), respectively. This indicates that clients who find the content on social media ads reliable and believable source are more open to have the willingness to buy the promoted products because the credibility of the sponsored social media ads is a profound influence on brand reputation and that may affect the purchase intention of the consumers. Therefore, when customers observe that advertising is trustworthy and reliable, they attempt to contemplate this ad as more valuable and worthy, leading to purchasing the promoted product or service. Based on the literature, several scholars supported that social media advertising's trustworthiness has positively affected consumers' purchase intention (Hamouda, 2018).

Lastly, the findings of the study showed that the consumer's overall perceived value of social media advertising positively influences purchase intention, and its effects were significant as the path of coefficient and P-value showed ($B=0.231$, and $p<0.005$), respectively. The customers with a positive perspective towards social media advertising are likely to produce beneficial behavioral actions. Therefore, the more desirable perspectives toward perceived value social networks advertising and marketing, the more positively consumers respond by getting the product or service marketed or seeking associated information about ads revealed on social media. Besides, the findings of many studies have supported that the consumers' perceived value toward social media advertising has positively influenced the consumers' purchase intention (Wang & Sun, 2010; Mir, 2012; Dao et al., 2014; Hamouda, 2018).

Implications

There are several academic and management impacts on the findings of this study. About the theoretical implications, the study first took into account the advertising value model developed

by [Ducoffe \(1996\)](#) for conventional ads into social media context. The efficiency and the applicability of the social media model have been verified by practical shreds of evidence in which the implementation of social media advertising is still progressing as it is new ([Hamouda, 2018](#)). Second, the study provides theoretical insights into how consumers' advertising beliefs regarding the new media, called social media, influence customers' purchase intention. Third, the study gives empirical assistance for the Expectancy Value Theory's appropriateness to social networks, a new advertising and marketing platform, in the context of Somalia, in which the use of social media in advertising is simply beginning to take hold. Lastly, the study enhances the understanding of social media marketing and advertising knowledge by offering additional proof about the impact social media sites might have on the classification of the product on the regarded social media sites value, which eventually influences the consumers' purchase intention.

From the managerial implication, this study attempts to understand the consumers' beliefs and attitudes toward the influence of social media advertising on their purchase intention, which marketing professionals might properly evaluate the execution of market communication mix approach entailed social media advertising and marketing. To put it simply, this research would undoubtedly be substantial in extracting the individual beliefs, which are the crucial determinants of consumer's favorability or unfavorability of social media advertising. After that, the marketing experts might establish their advertising mix based on the findings and the implications of this research study to accomplish the desired purposes. Furthermore, the present study's findings provided clues on the key attributes that must be the attention of marketers involved in social media advertising. Informativeness, for example, was revealed as an important aspect of the current study. Therefore, marketing professionals must place more effort

right into the high quality and the amount of information that exists. Updated and comprehensive information concerning all the product dimensions such as product feature and benefits, prices, accessibility, discounts, and distribution must be considered in any social media ads' messages ([Alalwan, 2018](#)).

Most importantly, social media ads must also concentrate on the value proposition of any products they advertise. Additionally, social media advertising's credibility and entertainment aspects are perceived as essential attributes that motivate consumers to react to the ads as positive or negative. Therefore, to be effective, social media marketers should maintain the authenticity and trustworthiness of their ads. Social media ads should be enjoyable or have amusement to the customers to attract their emotions, which brings to have a favorable reaction to the promoted product.

Conclusion

The relevant concerns of social media advertising and marketing have been significantly the focal point of both professional and researchers over the advertising area. For that reason, this research was carried out to increase the existing understanding concerning the major elements related to social media ads and their influence on the intention to purchase a product. After closely studying the literature related to this area, four primarily variables have been identified, including informativeness, entertainment, credibility, and overall perceived value of social media advertising as an essential predictor of consumers' purchase intention. The data was gathered from Mogadishu-Somalia by distributing a self-administrated questionnaire via social media, specifically Facebook and WhatsApp. After that, 182 finished as well as legitimate feedbacks were targeted for further evaluations in SPSS. Exploratory Factor analysis was performed to examine whether the data are suitable to further analysis. And finally, regression analysis was performed to test the

hypothesis of the study. All the independent factors (informativeness, entertainment, credibility, and perceived value of social media advertising) positively impact consumers' purchase intention. Therefore, it is recommended for marketing professionals to carefully plan and design their advertising campaigns to lure their target audiences' attention.

Limitation and Future research

All hypotheses of the study supported the conceptual framework of the study. However, the study encounters certain limitations. First, the study is conducted only in Somalia, which may make it difficult to be generalized the

findings of the study to other countries since there is cultural diversity. Therefore, there is a chance for conducting future research covering other countries. Similarly, the study just used limited social media advertising values while there are more values of social media ads. Hence, future studies other values such as interactivity and irritation. Another limitation is that there is no specific product or industry for assessing the impact of social media advertising values on purchase intention. Thus, future studies can address this gap. Finally, the study focused on Facebook as a social media advertising platform; therefore, future studies are recommended to investigate other social media platforms as an advertising tool.

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